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THE LATEST IN HWO NEWS

Spring 2026

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Project Updates

By Giada Arney - HWO Interim Project Scientist

Dear HWO Community,

Welcome to the inaugural issue of the [Habitable Worlds Observatory \(HWO\)](#) newsletter! HWO is NASA's next Astrophysics flagship mission, following in the tradition of other transformational missions like the Hubble Space Telescope, the James Webb Space Telescope, and the Roman Space Telescope. At the time it launches, HWO would be the most powerful observatory ever put into space. At far-ultraviolet, optical, and near-infrared wavelengths, it would peer into the universe with an unprecedented combination of sensitivity and resolution, enabling improved studies of known phenomena, but also allowing us to tackle entirely new questions in the realm of the ultra-faint and ultra-small. HWO would be able to study an astonishing range of targets, including early galaxies, diffuse matter flows between galaxies, nascent stars, black holes, ionizing radiation in the early universe, neutron star mergers, solar system worlds, near-earth asteroids, worlds beyond the solar system, and much more.

The discovery of life on another world would transform how we view our place in the cosmos "in a way not seen since the days of Copernicus" to borrow a quote from the [Astro2020 Decadal Survey](#). Habitable Worlds Observatory would be the first telescope designed to search for signs of habitability and life on planets outside of our solar system, observing the atmospheres of Earth-like exoplanets around Sun-like stars. But an Earth-sized planet is ten billion times dimmer than a star like our Sun, so next-generation technology is required to see these planets, search their atmospheres for biosignatures (remotely observable signs of life), and

evaluate any possible biosignatures in the context of their environments. HWO would deploy an advanced coronagraph as part of an [ultra-stable](#) observatory system designed to suppress starlight and reveal orbiting planets. We are on the path to maturing technologies HWO would require to achieve this visionary goal through major efforts in laboratory testbeds. Excitingly, the Roman Space Telescope is set to launch as early as this fall and includes a technology demonstration of critical technologies for HWO called the [Roman Coronagraph Instrument](#). This will be the first "active" coronagraph in space, meaning it is able to adjust for minute imperfections in the light path with technologies like deformable mirrors, and it will help prove and mature many of the critical technologies for HWO. Equally important, the Coronagraph Instrument on Roman is part of an ultra-stable observatory system: Roman will be the most stable telescope ever launched, which is crucial for coronagraph operations.

All of NASA's flagships have required audacious and bold thinking, and we are on the path that will turn HWO from a dream into reality. The HWO Technology Maturation Project Office (TMPO) formally initiated in August 2024 and is the project office for pre-phase A, the earliest NASA mission phase. TMPO, pronounced "tempo", evokes thoughts of music, and just like musicians in a symphony, each member of the team has a vital part to play in realizing this mission. The Project Office is maturing the technologies, developing the architectures, and refining the science to set HWO up for success. TMPO was joined by the Community Science and Instrument Team (CSIT) in June 2025. Together, TMPO and the CSIT have

carefully read over the more than 70 **HWO science cases** put forward by members of the scientific and technical community. We are so grateful to everyone for the thousands of collective hours that have been poured into these efforts, which are now helping shape the science goals for this observatory.

The HWO team has been extremely active over the last year. Last summer, hundreds of scientists and engineers came together at our inaugural community conference, **Towards the Habitable Worlds Observatory: Visionary Science and Transformational Technology**. It was wonderful to hear the excitement and ideas for this mission through an excellent compilation of talks, posters, panels, and conversations. A **conference proceedings volume** from this meeting will be out soon. Also, a SPIE JATIS HWO Special Section, called the **Habitable Worlds Observatory Pre-Formulation Science, Architecture Concepts, and Technology Maturation**, has received dozens of papers that are now undergoing peer review. We anticipate the complete SPIE JATIS Special Section being released by late summer. Additionally, we are soliciting submissions for a **RASTI** special issue on HWO mission concept development software, tools, and methodologies developed during the last few years. Recently, NASA announced the **selection of industry proposals** to mature critical core technologies for HWO. We know from the **NASA Large Mission Study** that it is important to mature critical technologies early, and the team is thrilled to be initiating

these efforts.

We are pleased to announce that within the last month, we have added four international ex-officio members to the CSIT. These members serve as points of contact for coordinating science activities and conveying the broad scientific perspectives of their space agencies and regional communities. These members are:

- European HWO Program Coordination Group: Anthony Boccaletti
- CSA: Jean Dupuis
- ESA: Paul McNamara
- JAXA: Takahiro Sumi

Stay tuned for more ways to get involved with HWO! At the American Astronomical Society meeting in January 2026, we announced that we will be soliciting proposals for instrument concept studies. More information on this opportunity and others is coming soon. You can join the **Habitable Worlds Observatory Science Interest Group (HWO SIG)** to stay involved with the HWO community. For those attending the upcoming **Astrobiology Science Conference** in May, please join us at our next community town hall. If you missed our presentations at previous meetings or are interested in other HWO materials, there is a repository in the **HWO Zenodo Community**. We plan to make this a central repository for all things HWO and will provide more information in a coming newsletter.

We're so thrilled to be on this exciting journey with you!

Giada Arney is a planetary scientist and astrobiologist at the NASA Goddard Space Flight Center. Her research focuses on understanding planetary habitability, potential biosignatures on exoplanets, and how studies of planets such as Venus inform the search for life beyond the solar system. Giada is interim Project Scientist for HWO and is working with the team to define the mission's science goals.

CSIT Updates

By David Charbonneau and Evgenya Shkolnik - CSIT Co-chairs

Over the past six months, the Habitable Worlds Observatory's Community Science & Instrument Team (CSIT) has focused on translating broad community science priorities into recommendations for concrete mission-driving requirements. The CSIT brings together expertise across exoplanets and habitability, the solar system, stars and stellar environments, galaxies and cosmic ecosystems, extreme astrophysics, and instrumentation. Our central task is to ensure that HWO's design is directly traceable to the science the community most values, serving as a bridge between community vision and mission architecture.

A major component of this work has been reviewing over 70 community Science Case Development Documents prepared by hundreds of community members and distilling them into a focused initial set of recommended Driving Science Cases that can inform draft Level 1 science requirements. In parallel, we are identifying Compelling Science Cases from the current slate of Science Case Development Documents to guide trade studies and Design Reference Missions.

From this process, the CSIT has recommended an initial set of five Driving Science Cases that span the

Community Science & Instrument Team (CSIT)

National Aeronautics and Space Administration

 David Charbonneau Co-chair Harvard	 Evgenya Shkolnik Co-chair ASU	 Michael Bottom UC Berkeley	 Eric Burns LSU	 Richard Cartwright JHU APL	 Ewan Douglas U. Arizona	 Kevin France LASP/CU Boulder
 Scott Gaudi Ohio State	 Rebecca Jensen-Clem UCSC	 Janice Lee STScI	 Victoria Meadows SETI / U. Washington	 Chris Packham UT San Antonio		
 Laurent Pueyo STScI	 Tyler Robinson U. Arizona	 Jason Tumlinson STScI	 Anthony Boccaletti E-HWO-PCG	 Jean Dupuis CSA	 Paul McNamara ESA	 Takáhiro Sumi JAXA

International ex-officio

HABITABLE
WORLD
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For more information visit nasa.gov/HWO

The HWO Community Science & Instrument Team

breadth of modern astrophysics. These are anchored by five overarching science questions:

- How do the most metal-poor massive stars power and shape their environments?
- How do ionizing photons drive the evolution of cosmic structure?
- Where did the heavy elements originate?
- How do mass and energy flow in and out of galaxies?
- Do other stars host planets with life?

Each of these questions is being translated into specific, measurable observatory capabilities. For example, understanding cosmic ionization and galaxy ecosystems requires high-throughput far- and near-ultraviolet spectroscopy, including multi-object spectroscopy and integral field units. Investigating extreme stars and the origin of heavy elements demands high-resolution ultraviolet spectroscopy and spatially resolved UV imaging. Addressing the question “Do other stars host planets with life?”

drives requirements for a telescope equipped with a high-performance coronagraph, broad wavelength coverage from the ultraviolet through the near-infrared, high-contrast imaging and spectroscopy, and precise astrometry to characterize Earth-like planets around Sun-like stars.

A key outcome of the CSIT’s work to date has been the translation of these science questions into preliminary observatory-level goals, explicitly linking community priorities to aperture size, wavelength coverage, spectral resolution, angular resolution, contrast performance, and field of view. As HWO advances toward its next major milestones, the CSIT will continue refining these mappings, supporting trade studies, and serving as ambassadors for the broader community. Our aim is to ensure that HWO remains a mission shaped by rigorous science, broad participation, and a clear line of sight from foundational questions to mission design.

David Charbonneau is an astronomer and professor at Harvard University whose research pioneered the detection and characterization of transiting exoplanets. His work probes the atmospheres and compositions of nearby worlds, and serves as Co-chair of HWO’s CSIT.

Evgenya Shkolnik is an astrophysicist and professor at Arizona State University whose research focuses on exoplanets and the environments of their host stars. She investigates how stellar activity affects planetary atmospheres and habitability, and serves as Co-chair of HWO’s CSIT.

UV Astrophysics Science

By Paul Scowen - HWO UVI Instrument Scientist

Complementing the ground-breaking coronagraphic performance needed for exoplanet science, the current HWO observatory concept is carrying notional astrophysics instruments to perform transformative science in both the ultraviolet (UV) and visible bands. The ultraviolet science focuses on taking advantage of the many spectral diagnostic lines in that waveband to diagnose the dynamics of both energy and material escaping galaxies. These

observations are essential to understand these dynamics that shape the intergalactic medium and potentially explain the reionization of the early universe. Coupled with the exquisite angular resolution of a telescope larger than 6 meters, several science cases are pushing the limits of the reach of the observatory to image the closest truly metal-poor galaxy, 1 Zw 18. By using 1 Zw 18 as a local analog, we can study what very metal-poor massive

The metal-poor massive star populations available to resolved spectroscopy at present (yellow region) and with HWO (pink region). The present state-of-the-art consists only of the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds (L/SMC), and a handful of metal-poor dwarf Irregular galaxies lacking higher mass stars. HWO will potentially enable UV observations of metal-poor ($\sim < 10\%$ solar) galaxies, such as 1 Zw 18, to study the formation, life, and death of the first generations of stars. (Senchyna et al. 2025)

stars—“cousins” to the first generations of stars in the distant universe—can tell us about star formation, life, and death in that era. Combined with the ultraviolet, HWO would give us, for the first time, critical information about this rare class of stars.

These science drivers demand particular performance on the part of the observatory. To capture the most important spectral diagnostics, the telescope must see into the "Far-UV" spectrum. This requires reaching wavelengths below 115 nm, which is the physical limit (or "cutoff") of the Magnesium Fluoride (MgF₂) coatings used on the Hubble Space Telescope's mirrors. To access wavelengths down to 100 nm, HWO must utilize Lithium Fluoride (LiF) coatings whose spectral properties allow access to shorter wavelengths. Furthermore, resolving individual massive stars in super-star clusters at the distance of the galaxy 1 Zw 18 requires the mirrors to be polished to a performance level well below the adopted diffraction limit wavelength of 500 nm. The optical quality must remain essentially the same at shorter wavelengths to provide

similar performance down to 100 nm. This extreme surface smoothness ensures that UV light is not scattered by microscopic imperfections in the mirror, allowing HWO to resolve individual stars within dense clusters at the distance of 1 Zw 18, and to accurately diagnose mass loss rates and ionizing radiation being emitted by those stars.

To these, and other ends, the technology development in the ultraviolet for HWO is currently focusing on putting out funding support calls for detector development to ensure HWO detectors are equipped with the right size, low noise, small pixels, and wavelength coverage to maximize our ability to detect faint UV photons at the necessary signal to noise. Additionally, we are investing in the uniform deposition of the protected LiF coatings at meter-class scales necessary for the anticipated size of the mirror segments in HWO's design. This effort aims to demonstrate that HWO mirror segments can be coated uniformly enough for the coronagraphy, while simultaneously providing the reflectivity down to 100 nm that the UV science demands.

Paul Scowen is a Senior Research Astrophysicist at the NASA Goddard Space Flight Center. His research interests have been focused on a better understanding of both the formation and evolution of massive stars and how they shape the evolution of galaxies. Paul serves as the Instrument Scientist for the Ultraviolet Instrument (UVI) for HWO which includes both the UV-MOS, the multi-object spectrograph, and the UV-IFU, the integral field unit.

JPL's Testbeds

By Caleb W. Baker - JPL HWO Testbed Lead

On the corner of Surveyor Rd and Arroyo Rd, conveniently situated across the street from the hustle, bustle, and heavy industry of JPL's main shipping & receiving bay, stands the fairly unassuming Building 318. The Optical & Interferometry Development Laboratory has stood guard over the morning commute traffic from JPL's south gate entrance since the early 2000s when it was commissioned as a state-of-the-art development facility for NASA's Space Interferometry Mission (SIM).

Over the ensuing two decades, Building 318 would house scientists, engineers, and technicians attempting to tackle some of the toughest challenges of precision optics and interferometry. Host to SIM's Micro-Arcsecond Metrology (MAM) testbed until the

project's cancellation, B318's high bay cleanroom would later become the home of the Exoplanet Exploration Program Office's (ExEP's) High Contrast Imaging Testbed (HCIT) facility as well as the proving ground for much of the fundamental physics and component technology that would eventually enable the Roman Space Telescope's Coronagraph Instrument.

Among its accolades, this facility lays claim to over a dozen flight and airborne instrument builds (many of JPL's imaging spectrometer fleet have gone through its lowbay), demonstrations of picometer-precision metrology (SIM), and several major, foundational performance records in the field of high contrast imaging ([Seo et al. 2019](#); [Allen et al. 2023](#)).

*Deer run along Surveyor Rd outside JPL's Building 318
(Photo credit: Caleb Baker)*

SIM's Micro-Arcsecond Metrology testbed

*Two world-record high contrast results attained in HCIT:
 Left: 4E-10, full annulus, at 10% bandwidth (Seo et al. 2019)
 Right: 4E-10, half-annulus, at 20% bandwidth (Allan et al. 2023)*

It may not be much surprise, then, that as NASA's HWO looks to establish the viability of a coronagraph operating at levels supporting Earth-like exoplanet detection, B318's HCIT facility features prominently on its list of critical facilities - next to other world-premiere labs at Goddard Space Flight Center, Ames Research Center, and NASA's many industry partners. Leveraging the wealth of heritage high contrast imaging experience at JPL, HWO has chartered the development of multiple coronagraphic systems testbeds specifically tailored to meet the project's needs, starting with a testbed dedicated to demonstrating the physics of nullifying starlight in quasi-static conditions.

One complication is that those needs are still under refinement. As HWO's science, integrated modelling, and systems engineering teams are hard at

work developing a series of Exploratory Architecture Concepts (EACs) intended to push the theoretical limits of the observatory's potential design and performance, the testbed team at JPL bears the responsibility not just to design a coronagraph but to design for potentially any coronagraph (...within reason).

Repurposing an existing HCIT testbed - the 2nd Decadal Survey Testbed (DST2) - in a bid to deliver on HWO's early quasi-static contrast milestones in a challenging funding and schedule environment, JPL's testbed team turned, for its quasi-static design, to a series of experts in Lyot, Vortex, and Apodizer designs (formal apologies to PIAA enthusiasts) as well as HWO's EAC optical designers to realize a highly flexible layout capable of supporting each of HWO's high-interest coronagraph architectures.

Engineers Garreth Ruane and Matt Noyes take a break after loading DST2's initial incarnation into B318's 40-foot vacuum chamber.

This design is more challenging than one might expect. Vortex coronagraphs prefer a long working F/# at the focal plane mask. Apozider-types prefer a wider beam at an upstream pupil plane to allow for good spatial resolution during mask manufacturing. Lyot-types demand optimal placement and stroke usage of the system's deformable mirrors (usually one DM at a pupil and the other at least 1 meter separated to give it control over field amplitude). In addition, reaching a contrast level never before reached ($\leq 1E-10$ contrast ratio) requires that attention be paid to other relatively mundane features such as

about a focal plane mask at a 3° AoI). All of these demands play against each other to inflate the design's mechanical footprint despite, like the rest of Southern California, open space being in short supply and high demand on the optical table. The resulting design contains a collimating arm working at F/60, a 33.75mm apodizer plane, an F/# of 40 at the focal plane mask, and enough space for 1mm-pitch DMs to be 1m apart. In addition, its F/46 science camera arm means that, for the testbed's 4.6-micron camera pixels, the camera's pixel/ λ /D resolution is a beautifully elegant $\lambda/100$ (a fact the

DST2's renovated optical layout supporting HWO coronagraphy.

extremely precise stray light control, a long source collimation arm to avoid spatially resolving small features of the testbed's simulated star, and supporting any transmissive optics at moderate angles of incidence to avoid ghost reflections (for a fun party game, ask any coronagrapher how they feel

lead optical designer was – and still is – quite enchanted by). The JPL team is also already working with a team from GSFC to accommodate an Integrated Field Spectrograph (IFS) for install and operation sometime after commissioning.

CAD model of DST2's renovated form.

This testbed design passed peer review by a panel of optical engineers and high contrast experts at JPL during the summer of 2025 and engineers have since been working to prepare for its alignment, characterization, and commissioning as the team's selected optical vendor manufactures the testbed's series of extreme-precision Off-Axis Parabola (OAP) mirrors. Barring delays of these critical components, the team is expecting to have the testbed aligned and characterized by the end

of spring, set for commissioning over the summer of 2026. Commissioning to a record-breaking level of starlight nullification is expected to be extremely challenging, but with decades of cumulative experience to draw from and some of the most precise and well-characterized optics on the planet, the team is hopeful that, for at least one small circle on a detector in JPL's Building 318 high bay cleanroom, the future is actually the opposite of bright.

Caleb W. Baker is an optical engineer and group supervisor at the Jet Propulsion Laboratory. He received his Ph.D. in Optics from the University of Arizona where he specialized in ultrafast semiconductor laser design and engineering. Since joining JPL he has worked on a variety of spaceflight optical systems including laser metrology, Psyche's Deep Space Optical Communication terminal, and Roman's Coronagraph Instrument. He currently leads JPL's coronagraphic systems testbed efforts for HWO.

Segments

A Profile on Lee Feinberg - HWO Principal Architect

by Jessica L. Noviello - HWO Executive Officer

June 3, 1991 was Lee Feinberg's first day at NASA Goddard. He remembers it exactly because of the circumstances that brought him to NASA in the first place. "Hubble launched in 1990, and they found the spherical aberration, and within a few months, I was already working on becoming a civil servant."

Now, after over three decades of working on NASA missions, Lee retired on February 27, 2026. What happened in between is a legendary career, including the role of telescope manager and optics lead for the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) and as the Principal Architect for the Habitable Worlds Observatory (HWO). Lee leaves an indelible mark on NASA Goddard and the projects he worked on yet

remains humbled by the work; he sees his career as a collection of service given to humanity via space exploration. So, who is the man behind the Principal Architect role? Jessica Noviello interviewed him to find out.

Lee began his career by studying optics at the University of Rochester and immediately started getting his hands on hardware. "As a student, one of the most exciting things I did was work at a laser fusion laboratory building interferometers. I did everything from procuring optics, aligning optics, writing the software, doing the analysis, so really, really good hands-on experience." In fact, he thinks that getting hands-on experience is the best way to learn, and says that being

Lee speaking about JWST at the ARTECHOUSE in Washington, DC, USA, in January 2024

thrown into the clean room at Goddard was “the best thing that happened to me” in terms of his career.

After graduating, Lee worked at different companies for a few years until the fateful launch of Hubble and the unfortunate discovery of the spherical aberration. He was then hired at Goddard to work on the first Hubble servicing mission, “helping to figure out which vendor to use for the corrective optics and testing the optics and doing integration testing.” Not long after, Lee became the instrument manager for the STIS ([Space Telescope Instrument Spectrograph](#)) instrument on Hubble. Later, he helped to lead the study for the [Wide Field Camera 3](#) instrument, which was installed as part of [Hubble Servicing Mission 4](#) in 2009. As if he wasn’t busy enough, Lee also earned a master’s in applied physics from the Johns Hopkins University along the way.

“I did a lot of Hubble,” he reminisced, smiling. “I was on Hubble for about 10 years total, and then I became the assistant chief for technology in the Instrument Systems and Technology division [at Goddard] for three years.” In this role, he helped get multiple novel ideas advanced and worked on an early technology demo proposal for the Next Generation Space Telescope. Lee then left NASA for a year for a startup company before returning to be the telescope manager for JWST.

Where JWST was in its development at that time is about where HWO is today. “That was 25 years ago.”

Lee’s path to HWO from this point on is straightforward, but its length might be surprising. “This HWO concept for me started back in 2008, so believe it or not, I’ve already been on this mission for a long time.” Lee became involved with one of the very first [ATLAST \(Advanced Technology Large-Aperture Space Telescope\)](#) studies, one that included a 9.2 m segmented concept. From then on, he was involved with “pretty much every study that was done” related to next-generation space telescopes, including [HabEx](#) and [LUVOIR](#). He also worked on the [Ultra-stable Observatory Roadmap Team](#) as a co-chair for the Technical Assessment Group, gaining valuable experience with testbeds and mission hardware. In mid-2024, he was officially named the Principal Architect role for HWO, the current working name for the top-recommended mission from the [Astro2020 Decadal Survey](#). But what is a Principal Architect exactly, and why did HWO need one?

The Principal Architect is a role unique to HWO born of the hard-won experiences of NASA employees from working on other missions. For the most part, NASA missions have a hierarchical structure that remains static throughout the mission’s duration. For a mission in development

Lee showing then-NASA Administrator Bill Nelson some of JWST's first images.

especially one as large and complex as HWO, that traditional framework would be too rigid to embrace major change. So, NASA leadership decided to try something new with the Principal Architect role. “The idea was a little bit like there are principal investigators on missions who make the final call on things. And we felt early on a lot of what we were doing was technology definition and architecture work. We weren't at a point where we could just run it like a project.”

Lee describes his role as a “Jack of all trades” position “with a very large dynamic range. Part of it is setting a high-level vision of how the architecture should be evaluated,

looking at lessons learned and heritage, and making sure we're doing things smarter.” This kind of knowledge only comes from firsthand experience, and Lee has that in spades along with a keen eye for details. “Part of that here was looking at lessons learned from large missions, from Webb, from Roman, and making sure that as we go, we're doing things like really maturing the concept. So I'm the person who has to make sure, or I was the person, who really tried to make sure that we were maturing the concept, but also that we weren't going down rabbit holes.”

Enhancing the culture of the HWO team is also a major part of why Lee was impactful as a leader, wisdom he

Lee presents HWO to the planetary sciences community at the town hall event at the 2025 American Geophysics Union fall meeting. (Photo credit: Megan Ansdell)

attributes to his family and his own personal values. “Valuing everybody on the team’s ideas, and valuing the diversity of people, and trying to be inclusive—these are all really important values that I think it’s important for the Principal Architect to have.”

When it comes to HWO, Lee is most looking forward to all it will discover that we don’t know about. “The absolutely most exciting part is when HWO surveys hundreds of Sun-like stars and we find out what’s there. Oxygen, water, methane, other biosignatures, I mean, that’s going to be momentous.... I think besides the stuff we know we’re looking for, it’s like, what are the surprises? The unexpected is as exciting as the expected.”

Lee’s attitude helped guide the HWO Project Office through the complexities involved in developing HWO’s scientific objectives, architecture, and story.

The way that the HWO team rose to the challenge is a source of pride for Lee. When asked what made him an effective leader during such a busy time for the mission, Lee credited his versatility and ability to make decisions quickly to his passion: music. “Fun fact about me: I’m obsessed with music. I play piano, I play in three bands, I played everything from jazz and blues to rock. I write music. I record music. Especially the jazz part. I really love improvising. In a lot of ways, [being] a jazz improv player in terms of dealing with things as they come at you and then figuring out how to incorporate them and seeing the big picture....If you look at a jazz solo, there’s the big picture of it, but then there’s the details of what scales and what transitions you’re using and all that. I think that makes me sort of interesting.”

His favorite musician? “Pat Metheny,

who's actually a guitar player, but his keyboardist for many years was one of my favorite keyboardists, Lyle Mays. And I will admit that I'm moving to Zurich and I already have tickets to see Pat Metheny in Zurich this summer."

Like many people associated with HWO, Lee feels that the mission is bigger than any one person or obstacle, and it motivates him to keep pushing forward. "Number one, I think just on a personal level, you don't want to have any regrets in life. You want to feel like you laid it all out there. That's definitely a part of what I would consider personal success is living a life that's fulfilled and happy. I think part of what we're trying to do [with HWO], honestly, is lift humanity up a little bit.

"One of my favorite parts of Webb was when it launched when there was a lot of craziness going on around the world, and so many people said to me: 'you know, it was so nice to have something so positive to look forward to.' I feel like HWO is going to be that kind of thing. It's the kind of thing that will unite everybody on the planet with a sense

of awe, and working on something like that to me is what it's all about."

Lee will be moving to ETH Zurich in Switzerland later in 2026 to work on the Large Interferometer to Find Exoplanets (LIFE) mission. He is excited for the new opportunity to work on a different mission, and will be watching from afar to see what we do next for HWO. He has some great ideas for where HWO should focus its efforts next; figuring out the path to becoming a regularly serviceable mission and exploring potential partnerships with industry are top of his mind.

Before he leaves, he has some advice for all of us: "I think we have a vision, so be bold. Explain yourself and go out there and explain to people why you're being bold. When you're bold, people get excited about it and people want to be part of it. But don't give up your vision."

Thank you, Lee, for your years of work at NASA and for what you've done for HWO. We hope you'll come back to see it launch!

Jessica L. Noviello is an assistant research scientist at the University of Maryland, Baltimore County affiliated with NASA Goddard Space Flight Center via the CRESST II Cooperative Agreement. Her research expertise is in the evolution of icy bodies in the Solar System, the cryovolcanic process, and the characterization of exoplanet interiors. She is also the Executive Officer of the HWO Technology Maturation Project Office.

Upcoming Events

Cross-PAG/SIG HWO Seminar

Update from CSIT - *Scott Gaudi*

O VI in Diffuse Media - *Sanch Borthakur*

<https://teams.microsoft.com/meet/21636500278946?p=4DwFedPzGP8APzgLK1>

Meeting ID: 216 365 002 789 46; Passcode: HT3ke7uU

Virtual - April 1, 2026, 10 PDT/1 EDT

HWO Red Wavelength Limit - *Kyle Cook*

Open Astro2030 Discussion - *Joe Burchett*

Pre-Proposal Workshop for HWO Instrument Concept Studies Solicitation

Washington, DC, USA + hybrid - May 4-5, 2026

NASA plans to solicit proposals for carrying out U.S.-led HWO instrument concept studies in spring 2026. In support of this solicitation, HTMPO will host a **hybrid** pre-proposal workshop. This workshop will give potential proposers the opportunity to learn about the interests of other potential proposers and to begin forming teams as appropriate. HTMPO will also provide updates on topics such as driving science cases, current HTMPO instrument concepts, and ongoing technology development; these updates will be recorded and made publicly available after the workshop. While in-person attendance will be limited by the venue size and offered on a first-come-first-serve basis, online attendance will be open. **Registration is free, but required, for both in-person and online attendance:** <https://cvent.me/NyvdDy>

HWO Town Hall @ AbSciCon

Madison, WI, USA - May 20, 2026

This **Town Hall** (11:45 AM - 12:45 PM on Wednesday May 20) will provide mission updates, including potential science that could be conducted with HWO, such as studying habitable exoplanets and Solar System objects. The final portion of the session will feature an "Open House" where HWO leadership and science team members will be available to session attendees for small-group discussions to engage on focused topic areas as well as receive community feedback.

Everything but Exoplanets: The Transformative General Astrophysics of HWO @ Summer AAS

Pasadena, CA, USA - June 14-18, 2026 (date TBD)

This Special Session will explore the many scientific opportunities beyond exoplanet studies that will be facilitated by HWO's unique capabilities, from utilizing unprecedented UV resolution to trace the "cosmic ecosystem" of gas and metals to investigations of galaxy growth and chemical enrichment across cosmic time. The session will also discuss HWO's role in probing the nature of dark matter, the demographics of black holes within the Milky Way, and the fundamental processes governing star and planet formation. This session is open to all AAS attendees and will feature an extended Q&A session for discussion and feedback from the community.

Engage

NASA HWO Website

<https://nasa.gov/HWO>

HWO Community Slack

Request to join the HWO Community Slack Workspace:

<https://tinyurl.com/hwoslack>

HWO Zenodo

Access HWO slides presented at community meetings:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/habitable-worlds-observatory>

HWO SIG

Get involved with the HWO Science Interest Group:

<https://science.nasa.gov/astrophysics/programs/physics-of-the-cosmos/community/hwo-sig/>

HWO News Mailing Lists

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